

Validation and Bias Analysis of TRITON/NEWT Lattice Physics Calculations for Cross-Section Generation: PWR Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Lattice physics transport calculations are essential for three-dimensional reactor core calculations with core simulators. This work presents a SCALE-TRITON/NEWT based approach for lattice calculations developed and validated for a representative pressurized water reactor (PWR). The validation methodology employs continuous-energy Monte Carlo simulations as high-fidelity reference, with a systematic bias analysis performed through intermediate model simplifications to isolate the impact of the involved approximations. Validation parameters include infinite multiplication factor, pin power distributions, actinide isotopic concentrations and fission fractions, relevant for characterizing the neutron source in reactor pressure vessel fluence analysis. Results demonstrate that the proposed model successfully completes multi-step burnup calculations within reasonable computational time while maintaining most target accuracy margins.

Keywords: SCALE, TRITON/NEWT, LTO, bias analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Long-term operation (LTO) of nuclear power plants (NPPs) is among the most critical topics in the nuclear industry, with substantial research efforts addressing technical challenges for extending plant lifetimes beyond their original design basis. Different national and international projects—e.g., Spanish *Plan Nacional FLEXCORE* and European EVEREST project respectively—exemplify these efforts. A primary objective is to assess the benefits of advanced multi-physics modelling for reactor pressure vessel (RPV) fluence calculations and provide guidance for more realistic RPV aging assessments in LTO licensing procedures.

The RPV fluence analysis methodology at UPM uses the two-step approach, common in industrial applications: in-core transport calculations to determine neutron source distribution, followed by fixed-source ex-core transport calculations to propagate neutrons to the RPV. In-core 3-D deterministic transport calculations can use either conventional nodal or advanced pin-by-pin modelling. Both require prior lattice transport calculations to generate homogenized reaction cross-sections for each fuel assembly (FA) type. This work validates the calculation scheme for cross-section generation via SCALE's TRITON/NEWT sequence for a representative Siemens/KWU Vorkonvoi PWR FA lattice from Grohnde NPP.

The validation is performed by comparing deterministic TRITON/NEWT results against reference Monte Carlo continuous-energy calculations using TRITON/KENO-VI. Several different modelling approaches are compared for two primary objectives: to assess the adequacy and accuracy of the deterministic lattice physics results; and to quantify and analyse the modelling biases introduced by various approximations (e.g., multigroup energy discretization, deterministic transport method, spatial and angular discretization).

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2. CODES AND BIASES

2.1 Codes Used: TRITON/KENO-VI and TRITON/NEWT

KENO-VI is a Monte Carlo (MC) criticality code that performs 3-D neutronic calculations in both continuous energy (CE) and multigroup (MG) modes. In KENO-CE mode, there are no spatial, angular, or energetic approximations, serving as a reference model for validation.

NEWT is a MG discrete-ordinates (S_n) radiation transport code that performs 2-D neutron transport calculations. Its Extended Step Characteristic (ESC) differencing scheme uses a computational mesh based on arbitrary polygons, providing flexibility for complex lattice geometries.

TRITON is a SCALE control module that performs depletion calculations by coupling transport solvers with the ORIGEN depletion code. It utilizes either deterministic transport codes (NEWT for 2-D) or MC codes (KENO-VI for 3-D) in both MG and CE modes. TRITON/NEWT combines 2-D transport with ORIGEN depletion calculations to generate lattice physics parameters and homogenized cross-sections for core simulator calculations.

2.2 Approaches Description

This work makes use of a generic Siemens/KWU Vorkonvoi PWR 16×16 FA lattice with 20 guide tubes and 8 Pyrex burnable absorber rods, depleted from 0 to 60 GWd/MTU. The five modelling approaches considered are described below.

The **TRITON/KENO-CE**—hereafter referred to as T/KENO-CE—approach uses ENDF/B-VII.1 CE neutron and gamma library. At each burnup step, it performs 3-D MC transport criticality calculations coupled with ORIGEN depletion, using 200 generations with 600,000 histories each and 10 skipped generations, achieving ± 10 pcm standard deviation in k_{inf} and $\pm 0.2\%$ standard deviation in pin power distribution. In the TRITON burnup scheme, each pin is depleted individually.

The **T/KENO-MG** approach simplifies the previous one by using the 56-group ENDF/B-VII.1 neutron library and thereby requiring self-shielding calculations. The MG approximation requires preliminary transport calculations to generate a characteristic pin cell spectrum for weighing processed nuclear data and producing a problem-dependent library. Self-shielding calculations in all MG approaches are performed via BONAMI (Bondarenko method) for the upper and lower energy range, and via CENTRM/PMC latticecell option for the point wise (resonances) range, which performs 2-D MoC transport with reflective boundary conditions at the pin-cell level [1]. This option, optimized for fuel pins and limited to four mixtures (pellet, gap, cladding, and coolant) was also applied for Pyrex burnable absorbers and guide tubes. For Pyrex burnable absorbers, the first and third layers represent homogenized regions of the pin cell, while the absorber material occupies the second layer. The fourth layer contains a homogeneous mixture of the surrounding cells, including the outer moderator of the non-fissile pin cell. The pin pitch is set to three times the standard value. Finally, guide tube models are also shielded to generate cross sections for water and guide tube cladding. Fig. 1 shows a representative scheme of the reality and self-shielding model for both Pyrex and guide tube pin-cells. Again, in the TRITON burnup scheme, each pin is depleted individually.

The **T/NEWT-DETAILED** approach employs the same library and self-shielding options as T/KENO-MG. As a deterministic approach, level-symmetric $S_n=16$ quadrature and 12×12 spatial discretization were applied. According to [2], these angular and spatial discretizations provide sufficient resolution to be classified as a fine-mesh configuration. Since NEWT computational cells are limited to polygons, cylindrical geometries were approximated using 36-sided polygons. Scattering anisotropy was treated with P3 expansion for moderator mixtures and P1 for all other materials. No approximations are included regarding the TRITON burnup scheme, and each pin is depleted individually.

Figure 1. Real and self-shielding models for non-fissile pins. Adapted from [3]

The **T/NEWT-ASSIGN** approach shares essentially the same input as T/NEWT-DETAILED but introduces an approximation in the TRITON burnup scheme: although each pin is depleted individually, self-shielding transport calculations are performed only for three representative fuel pins (inner, periphery, and corner) and then assigned to similar pins throughout the lattice. This approximates fuel pins self-shielded cross-sections. According to [4], studies have shown that this approach maintains solution accuracy for a wide range of assembly designs while significantly reducing run time.

The **T/NEWT-SIMP** approach introduces a greater simplification with respect to T/NEWT-DETAILED: only three fuel pin mixture types are self-shielded and depleted (inner, periphery, and corner). This neglects local burnup effects due to proximity to guide tubes or burnable absorbers.

2.3 Biases Breakdown

In a previous study [3], the biases introduced by each approximation were analysed for different types of pins without considering depletion. The present work aims to extend this bias analysis to an entire lattice containing burnable absorbers, guide tubes, and fuel pins under burnup conditions.

The MG energy discretization introduces two sources of bias: the 56-group ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library bias and the self-shielding calculation bias. This combined effect is termed here as the Multi-Group and Self-Shielding (**MGSS**) bias, and can be quantified as:

$$\epsilon_{MGSS} (pcm) = k_{\infty}^{T/KENO-MG} - k_{\infty}^{T/KENO-CE} \quad (1)$$

Deterministic Transport (**DT**) bias arises from the shift from MC to deterministic modelling, involving different approximations due to energy (multigroup), angular (Sn), and spatial discretization. Since the energy approximation is already captured in the MGSS bias, the DT bias reflects solely the coarse angular and spatial approximations, and can be quantified as:

$$\epsilon_{DT} (pcm) = k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-DETAILED} - k_{\infty}^{T/KENO-MG} \quad (2)$$

Two approximations of the **T/NEWT-DETAILED** approach are presented: **T/NEWT-ASSIGN** approach (**approximation 1**), which simplifies self-shielding treatment along depletion (Self-Shielding Assigned or SSA bias), and the **T/NEWT-SIMP** approach (**approximation 2**), which groups fuel pins for depletion (Grouped Fuel Mixtures or GFM bias). They are defined as:

$$\epsilon_{SSA} (pcm) = k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-ASSIGN} - k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-DETAILED} \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_{GFM} (pcm) = k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-SIMP} - k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-DETAILED} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the biases due to a coarse spatial and angular discretization have also been analysed for both approximations. A comparison between the T/NEWT-ASSIGN, also defined as "fine" (Sn =16, 12x12), and the same approach with a "coarse" discretization (Sn = 6, 4x4)[†] can be conducted. This results in the Spatial and Angular Discretization (SAD) bias for SSA (SAD-SSA) and GFM (SAD-GFM) approaches, defined as:

$$\epsilon_{SAD-ASS} (pcm) = k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-ASSIGN_{coarse}} - k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-ASSIGN_{fine}} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_{SAD-GFM} (pcm) = k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-SIMP_{coarse}} - k_{\infty}^{T/NEWT-SIMP_{fine}} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2 shows a diagram of the different approaches and biases. Finally, the total bias can be calculated for each approximation making use of the following expressions:

$$\epsilon_{Total\ ASSIGN} = \epsilon_{MGGS} + \epsilon_{DT} + \epsilon_{SAA} + \epsilon_{SAD-SAA} \quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon_{Total\ SIMP} = \epsilon_{MGGS} + \epsilon_{DT} + \epsilon_{GFM} + \epsilon_{SAD-GFM} \quad (8)$$

Computational time for each approach is represented in Table I. Note that the MC approaches were run using 20 parallel processors, and deterministic approaches were run using a single processor.

Table I. Run time for all approaches

	T/K-CE	T/K-MG	T/N-DET	T/N-ASSIGN fine	T/N-SIMP fine	T/N-ASSIGN coarse	T/N-SIMP coarse
Run time (hours)	331.4	191.8	103.4	26.6	17.6	7.2	2.2

Figure 2. Approaches schemes and biases diagram

2.4 Target and Acceptance Accuracy for Lattice Physics Codes

Acceptance accuracy represents the maximum allowable difference between the reference and the calculated response. If a test fails to meet this acceptance criteria, it must undergo detailed investigation. Target accuracy defines the desired level of agreement between the reference and the calculated values.

[†] Following SCALE's User Manual recommendations for spatial and angular discretization in NEWT [4]

If a test meets the acceptance accuracy but does not reach the target accuracy, it is considered valid but requires further analysis. For PWR, the criteria used is described below [5]:

- **k_{inf} and pin power target accuracy:** 200 pcm difference in k_{inf} , 0.5% Root Mean Square (RMS) difference in pin power distribution and 1.5% maximum difference in pin power distribution.
- **k_{inf} and pin power acceptance accuracy:** 400 pcm difference in k_{inf} , 1.5% RMS difference in pin power distribution and 2.5% maximum difference in pin power distribution.
- **Isotopic concentration target accuracy:** 1.5% relative difference in uranium and plutonium isotopes masses.
- **Isotopic concentration acceptance accuracy:** 2.5% relative difference in uranium and plutonium isotopes masses.

3. RESULTS

3.1 k_{inf} and Pin Power Difference

The k_{inf} and pin power differences between all analysed approaches and the reference calculation are shown in Fig. 3 and 5 respectively. Target accuracy is marked by a dotted grey line and acceptance accuracy by a dotted red line.

Concerning k_{inf} (see Fig. 3) all approaches fall within acceptance margins, and most of them also fall within target accuracy. T/KENO-MG exceeds target accuracy beyond 40 GWd/MTU and T/NEWT-DETAILED beyond 50 GWd/MTU. Concerning pin-powers (see Fig. 5), all approaches fall within target accuracy except for the T/NEWT-SIMP approach, which does not satisfy acceptance accuracy either.

Let us now analyse the bias breakdown. The MGSS bias (resulting from the MG approximation and self-shielding treatment in T/KENO-MG), remains within target accuracy up to 40 GWd/MTU, reaching a maximum k_{inf} difference of 277 pcm by 50 GWd/MTU (see Fig. 4). This difference falls well within acceptance criteria, therefore validating the applied self-shielding approach. For high FA burnup, MGSS positive bias leads to overestimating k_{inf} .

The DT bias (resulting from the shift to a deterministic approach in T/NEWT-DETAILED) is expected to be the most significant. Indeed, it falls within the target accuracy up to 42.5 GWd/MTU (see Fig. 4). A relevant underestimation of k_{inf} is observed for high FA burnups, with a maximum deviation of 680 pcm.

Figure 3. k_{inf} differences for different approaches

Approximation 1 enables evaluating the Self-Shielding Assign (SSA) bias (resulting from approximating the self-shielded cross-sections in T/NEWT-ASSIGN). The SSA bias follows a similar trend to the MGSS one but with smaller magnitude. Total bias in Fig. 4 results from compensating effects, particularly the positive MGSS and SSA biases offsetting the negative DT bias in the second half of the burnup range. This total bias (calculated via Eq. 7) exactly matches k_{inf} difference between T/NEWT-ASSIGN coarse and T/KENO-CE, confirming bias decomposition consistency. The T/NEWT-ASSIGN approach provides accurate k_{inf} and pin power distribution estimates within target margins, positioning itself as the most promising approach. Both DETAILED and ASSIGN models remain within the acceptance criterion, though a trend shift appears beyond ~ 30 GWd/THM, as explained in section 3.2, due to fission fraction differences—driven by Pu^{239} at low burnup and by U^{235} and Pu^{241} at higher burnup. It is worth mentioning that a coarser discretization, whose effect is evaluated by the SAD-SSA bias, has a negligible impact along burnup but an important impact on computational time (see Table I).

Figure 4. Biases Breakdown and Total Bias for each approach

Approximation 2 enables evaluating the Grouping Fuel Mixtures (GFM) bias (resulting from grouping fuel pins for depletion in T/NEWT-SIMP). The total bias calculated using Eq. 8 exactly matches k_{inf} difference between T/NEWT-SIMP and T/KENO-CE, demonstrating again the bias breakdown consistency. GFM bias completely offsets DT bias, leading to a particularly good k_{inf} estimation, even improving T/NEWT-ASSIGN results due to bias compensation. However, since it only depletes three fuel mixtures, individual pin power distributions deviate significantly from the reference (see Fig. 5), failing acceptance criteria and thus being rejected.

Figure 5. RMS and maximum pin power difference for each approach

3.2 Isotopic Concentration and Fission Fraction Difference

An **isotopic concentration** analysis along burnup was performed by comparing uranium and plutonium isotopes masses. Fig. 6 shows the relative difference in isotopic concentration for U^{234} , U^{235} , U^{238} , Pu^{239} , Pu^{240} , Pu^{241} , and Pu^{242} predicted by T/KENO-MG and T/NEWT-ASSIGN with respect to T/KENO-CE. T/KENO-MG (Fig. 6 left) provides an excellent estimate for all isotopes, falling within target accuracy except for U^{235} , which enters the acceptance accuracy margins beyond 50 GWd/MTU.

For T/NEWT-ASSIGN coarse (Fig. 6 right), all relative differences remain within acceptance criteria. Pu^{239} concentration is underestimated for low FA burnup and becomes overestimated for high burnups. Overall, these results confirm the approach's suitability for estimating isotopic concentrations.

Figure 6. Relative difference in FA-averaged U and Pu isotopic concentration

Table II presents average **fission fractions** calculated with KENO-CE (reference), and Fig. 7 displays RMS difference in fission fraction estimation across different approaches. Target and acceptance criteria for fission fraction estimations are not explicitly defined in the literature. To avoid estimation errors derived from averaged integral values, criteria were established based on individual pin power distributions (analysing RMS and maximum differences at the pin level) rather than relying on aggregated fission fraction values across the assembly.

U^{235} fails to reach acceptance accuracy in the ASSIGN and DETAILED models beyond 45 GWd/THM due to the DT bias, especially important by the end of the burnup range. Pu^{239} accumulates up to about 30 GWd/THM, after which its production and consumption reach equilibrium. The largest discrepancies among deterministic models occur during the rapid buildup phase, where the nuclide's low concentration amplifies uncertainties. As shown in Figure 7 (right), the DT bias peaks at low burnup, becomes negligible near Pu -239 saturation, and turns slightly negative afterward. This results in a bias increase between MGSS and DT models up to 30 GWd/THM, which is partially compensated by the SAD-SSA correction.

Table I. Averaged KENO-CE Fission Fractions

Burnup GWd/MTU	0	10	20	30	40	50	60
U^{235}	0.94	0.65	0.49	0.35	0.24	0.16	0.10
Pu^{239}	0.00	0.26	0.37	0.45	0.51	0.55	0.58
Pu^{241}	0.00	0.02	0.06	0.11	0.15	0.19	0.21
U^{238}	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.10
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99 [‡]	0.99	0.99 [§]

[‡] By 40 MWd/MTU other important fission fraction contributors are: Pu^{240} (0.14%) and U^{236} (0.12%)

[§] By 60 MWd/MTU, they are Cm^{245} (0.32%), Pu^{240} (0.2%) and both U^{236} and Pu^{238} (0.14%)

Figure 7. RMS difference in average fission fraction for U-235 and Pu-239.

CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to validate a deterministic lattice physics methodology for cross-section generation to be employed in 3-D core analyses. A systematic evaluation of different modelling biases was conducted to identify the most accurate and computationally efficient calculation scheme. The validation focused on four key parameters across a 60 GWd/MTU burnup range: reactivity metrics via k_{inf} , pin power distributions, isotopic concentration evolution, and relevant actinides fission fractions.

The systematic analysis revealed that it is possible to compensate for the biases derived from the MG and DT approximations. Comparisons against established acceptance and target accuracy criteria indicate that the TRITON/NEWT ASSIGN coarse model provides the best overall compromise between accuracy and computational efficiency, making it the preferred approach for cross-section generation in subsequent full-core simulations. Further analysis is being conducted to quantify biases across different fuel assembly configurations.

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